

Acquisition of Information and Communication Technology skills: Digital Literacies in Early Years in Nigerian Schools.

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Abstract:

The study investigated the primary school pupils' acquisition of information and communication skills in line with digital literacies. The sample size consists of 22 primary school pupils who were exposed to practical ICT training for 4 weeks (a month). The instrument for data collection were observation and in interview. The data were analyzed using percentages mean and t-test. It was found that the pupils were highly enthusiastic to acquire computer skills. Pupils, seven years could not carry out some of the tasks. Based on the findings, implications, recommendations and conclusions were drawn.

Introduction:

Digital literacy extends beyond basic reading and writing skills to include the ability to effectively use digital tools and technologies. It encompasses skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving and ethical use of information online. Information and communication technologies are gradually occupying the center stage in the affairs of human beings. Particularly, ICT is having a revolutionary effect on educational pedagogy and methodology worldwide. Eshet- Alkalai (2004) highlighted the multifaceted nature of digital literacy, which includes photo-visual literacy, reproduction literacy, branching literacy, information literacy and socio-emotional literacy. Wadi & Sonica (2003) observed that ICT have the potential to enhance educational quality by increasing motivation, facilitating acquisition of basic skills, promoting inquiry and exploration and preparing the young learners/individual for the technology driven world. It is a known fact that an effective teaching/learning process must stimulate intellectual curiosity and offer a sense of enjoyment that will move the students from the passive role of recipients of information to that active role of budders of knowledge. Gonthi (1993) stated that "ICTs are effective instructional aids to engage students in learning process. Computer multimedia, videos and television software provide information that can be authentic and challenging in addition to stimulating pupils' sensorial apparatus through images, color, sound, and movement. All these get learners motivated. Transmitting of accumulated knowledge to new generations is an essential component of the educational process. This knowledge includes basic skills and information that are the foundation of more complete knowledge.

Generally, evidence from many studies suggest that the use of ICT, particularly computer technologies is correlated to positive academic outcomes, including higher test scores, better attitudes toward schools and better understanding of abstract concepts. (Melmed, 1995 and Schacter, 1999). Furthermore, the secondary benefits of ICT in education is to familiarize new generations with the technologies that have become integral components of the modern world.

Constructive theorist believe that children need to have the opportunity to construct their own knowledge through play and exploration, so that they can create, reflect upon and workout their own understanding (Vygosky, 1978). Offering young children the opportunity to explore technology allows

Cognitive developmental approaches place "special emphasis on how individuals actively construct their thinking. According to Piaget (1954), individuals go through four stages of development namely.

1. Sensorimotor - 0 to 2 year

2. Preoperational - 2 to 7 years
3. Concrete operational - 7 to 11 years
4. Formal operational - 11 to adulthood

Elkin, 1976; Heuwinkel, 1996 in Santrock (2005) described ideas in Piaget's Theory that can be applied to teaching children as follows:

1. Take constructivist approach-children learn best when they are active and seek solutions for themselves rather than when they are passive.
2. Facilitate, rather than direct learning.
3. Consider the child's knowledge and level of thinking.
4. Use ongoing assessment.
5. Promote the students intellectual health.
6. Turn the classroom into a setting for exploration and discovery.

The Nigerian educational system has had major structural changes over the last 30 years. The current phase of evolution in Nigeria is directed towards the transition from traditional pedagogical methodology to more sophisticated technology based instructional methodology (Mac-Ikemenjima, 2003). The national policy on education deals with all aspects of education, from its philosophy, different levels and structure, financing, types of education to educational services, administration and planning of education. Greater emphasis is laid on the primary level of education. This is because it forms the foundation for proper development of literacy of all kinds. The curriculum objectives at the primary school level according to the National Policy on Education (FRN 2004) include:

- The inculcation of permanent literacy and numeracy, and the ability to communicate effectively,
- The laying of a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking
- Citizenship education as a basis for effective participation in, and contribution to the life of the society.
- Character and moral training and the development of sound attitudes
- Developing in the child the ability to adapt to his or her changing environment
- Giving the child opportunities for developing manipulative skills to function effectively in the society within the limits of his or her capacity.
- Providing basic tools for further educational advancement, including preparation for trades and crafts of the locality.(p 16)

The present research is borne out of the fifth objective above: developing in the child the ability to adapt to his or her changing environment. ICT is bringing a lot of revolutionary changes in our environment. Consequently sensitization on means of fitting into these revolutionary changes is of utmost importance. The Nigerian Government has made computer or ICT education compulsory at all levels of education. This programme faces enormous challenge observation of most school activities revealed that practical were never done. Moreover, greater percentages of the class teachers who teach this subject are not ICT literate. What the pupils do most of the time was to draw the computer and its peripherals and label. Hence they are not exposed to practical exercises and this affect negatively the acquisition of ICT skills.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to find the influence of mental development on ICT skill acquisition of primary school pupils. Specifically the study intends to:

1. Find out the dispositions of primary school children to practical ICT training
2. Assess the level of skills they can acquire after the training.

Research Questions

Two research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are primary school children disposed to practical ICT training?
2. What level of skills can they acquire?

Hypothesis

H₀ : There is no significant difference in the mean level of skill acquisition before and after training.

Methodology

The design of the study was descriptive survey: The population consisted of all the pupils in the University of Nigeria staff primary school. The sample used for the study was a total of 22 pupils, who registered for ICT training at the RESOURCE APPLICATION LIMITED, Zik Avenue, Uwani, Enugu. RESOURCE APPLICATION LIMITED is a private organization which specialized in ICT training for all cadres of personnel. They also provide the general public access to information super highway at a cost. In July 2006, RESOURCE APPLICATION LIMITED advertised ICT training for primary school children from 1st August to 31st August. The training period was three times a week with 2 hours per contact day. The training was open for primary 1 - 6 pupils and the following content areas were covered for them:

1. History of Computer
2. Importance of ICT
3. Identification of parts of a computer
4. Functions of different parts of a computer
5. Typing alphabets and numbers
6. Painting
7. Working with Ms-Word
8. Working with PowerPoint
9. Media player
10. Computer games

The content areas tested for practical's are 3-10 above. For each contact, the pupils were taught for about 1 hour and then allowed to practice for about 1 hour or more. The pupils were allowed free access and interaction with the systems. They were instructors to help them when they needed help. Similarly the pupils had opportunity to discuss with their peers.

The instruments for data collection were interview and observation. The researcher sat in for observation most of the days. The data were analyzed using percentages mean and t-test. Formal and informal interviews were conducted; individually and in small groups.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Observation schedule for disposition of primary school children to practical ICT training

S/N	Disposition to ICT Training	Percentage (%)
1	Attendance	90.8%
2	Punctuality	70.3
3	Commitment	95.1
4	Interaction / collaboration	98.2
5	Initiative	93.7
6	Enthusiasm	99.5

Observation of the pupils showed that they were very enthusiastic. Their attendance was very regular and punctuality moderate. Those who were occasionally late complained that it was caused by their parents or guardians who were supposed to drop them with their cars. Immediately after the instruction, they usually carry out the practical with deep concentration. They discussed among themselves, shared ideas and the older ones usually helped the younger ones out. The official dismissal time for the training was 12p.m., but many of them stayed as long as the laboratory was free or up to the time their parents came for them. Surprising the older ones went beyond the course content. Some of them went into Internet browsing and exchange of E-mails.

This finding agrees with the view of Wadi & Sonia (2003) and Gorithi (1993) that ICT have the potential to enhance educational quality by increasing motivation. It is also in line with the view of Resso (2000) that ICT can restore curiosity to education through inquiry and exploration which are essential for

critical thinking and creativity. It also supports the view of Maria (2001) that children who use technology in meaningful, relevant experiences, have an increased level of self-confidence as they rely less on their teacher and more on themselves for knowledge

Table 2: Level of Skill Acquisition.

S/N	Skills	Before Training				After Training			
		EW	VW	MW	NA	EW	VW	MW	NA
1	Can identify different peripherals of a system	0 (0)	4 (18.2)	8 (36.4)	10 (45.5)	17 (77.3)	2 (9.1)	3 (13.6)	0 (0)
2	Can use the mouse	3 (13.6)	3 (13.6)	4 (18.2)	12 (54.5)	16 (72.7)	2 (9.1)	3 (13.6)	0 (0)
3	Can turn on the system	2 (9.1)	3 (13.6)	3 (13.6)	14 (63.6)	16 (72.7)	3 (13.6)	3 (13.6)	2 (9.1)
4	Can identify and select files	0 (0)	2 (9.1)	2 (9.1)	18 (81.8)	19 (86.4)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)
5	Can use media player (music)	0 (0)	1 (4.5)	2 (9.1)	18 (81.8)	18 (81.8)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)
6	Can play games	1 (4.5)	3 (13.6)	6 (27.3)	12 (54.5)	16 (72.7)	2 (9.1)	2 (9.1)	1 (4.5)
7	Can use MS-word	2 (9.1)	4 (18.2)	6 (27.3)	11 (50)	19 (86.4)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	0 (0)
8	Can change font sizes	0 (0)	1 (4.5)	2 (9.1)	19 (86.4)	18 (81.8)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)
9	Can do painting	2 (9.1)	2 (9.1)	2 (9.1)	16 (72.7)	20 (90.9)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	0 (0)
10	Can type in letters and numbers	2 (9.1)	4 (18.2)	6 (27.3)	11 (50)	20 (90.9)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	0 (0)

EW – Excellently well; VW-Very well; MW - Moderately well, NA -Not at all
The numbers in parentheses are the percentages.

Table 1 showed that before the training only 0% --13.6% could carry out the skills excellently well, 4.5 to 18.2% could carry them out very well, 9.1 - 36.4% could carry them out moderately well while 45.5 to 86.4% could not carry out the activities.

However, after the training, 72.7% to 90.9% of the sample could carry out the skills excellently well, 45 - 90% could carry out the skills very well, and 4.5 - 13.6% could carry out the skills moderately well. 4.5 - 9.1% was unable to carry out some of the skills like turning on the system, identification and selection of files, using media player (music), playing games, and changing font sizes.

Observation showed that those unable to carry out some of the programmes are those from 6 years and below. Those from 7 years and above were able to carry out the programmes to some extent after the training.

Moreover, those who were discovered to be able to carry out some of the tasks excellently well before the training, had home computers and are also allowed to use these systems regularly. The finding is in line with Piaget (1954) and Vygotsky's (1978) theories of mental development. Those children from 7 to 11 years who were able to perform all the tasks excellently well are already in the operational stage which is characterized by logical reasoning about events, ability to understand the concept of conservation ability to organize objects into hierarchical classes and ability to place objects in ordered series.

On the other hand, children 4-6 years were unable to perform some of the tasks. This is still in consonant with the theory of mental development. This stage agrees with Piaget's preoperational stage which is characterized by egocentrism and centration which constitute constraints to the child's thinking.

Table 2(b): Mean and standard deviation of the Level of Skill acquisition before and after training.

S/N	Skills	Before Training			After Training		
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Can identify different peripherals of a system	22	1.68	.780	22	3.64	.727
2	Can use the mouse	22	1.86	1.125	22	3.64	.727
3	Can turn on the system	22	1.68	1.041	22	3.68	.646
4	Can identify and select files	22	1.27	.631	22	3.73	.767
5	Can use media player (music)	22	1.18	.501	22	3.68	.780
6	Can play games	22	1.68	.894	22	3.59	.854
7	Can use MS-Word	22	1.91	1.019	22	3.73	.767
8	Can change font sizes	22	1.18	.501	22	3.59	.959
9	Can do painting	22	1.55	1.011	22	3.86	.468
10	Can type in letters and numbers	22	1.91	1.019	22	3.86	.468

Table 2b showed that the overall mean for skill acquisition before the training was 1.47 after 3.37. The mean for all the skills before the training were below the benchmark of 3.00 while that after the training were above 3.00. This means that the level of skill acquisition was high.

Table 3: t-test of Skill Acquisition Before and After Training.

	N	MEAN	SD	Df	tcal	tcrit	Decision
Before	22	1.47	0.29	42	-29.1	2.021	Significant
After	22	3.37	0.1	42			

Table 3 shows that the critical value of t is higher than the calculated value indicating that there is significant difference in the level of skill acquisition before and training. More skills were acquired after the training.

Implications of the findings

It is imperative from the study that from primary one a child is already disposed for the use of ICT and the proficiency increases with age. ICT skills are the main information age learning skills. These include dynamic exploration, problem solving, inquiry, collaboration, and media handling (Hedberg & Harper 1996). These skills are better developed earlier in life. So among the global challenges facing educational systems the world over is the effective integration of ICT education through proper training at primary level of education for subsequent transmission to higher levels. This, if properly done will bring about enhancement strategies and also the achievement of the millennium development goals (MDGS).

Recommendations

The research recommends the following, based on the findings of the study.

- 1 Primary school administrators should explore and establish partnership for the ICT practical of the pupils.
- 2 Schools can bring in experts to teach the pupils, if schools have the systems or send the pupils to establishments that have the systems for training.
- 3 Parents should be encouraged to allow the children to make use of the systems at home instead of feeling that they will damage the systems. With proper guidance the risk of damage would be less.
- 4 Teachers should be encouraged to join their pupils in whatever form the partnership would take. This

would enable them to improve themselves.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have shown that primary school children are highly disposed and very enthusiastic to ICT training. From 7 years the children could acquire as much ICT skills as possible. Moreover availability of home computers increases their performance. Therefore it is pertinent that ICT programme for primary school is broadened and viable plans for implementation made. This is because; the foundation is laid at this stage.

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